

BRINGING THE MEMORIES HOME: INDIGENOUS DATA SOVEREIGNTY IN THE PRESERVATION OF RESIDENTIAL SCHOOL PHOTOS

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Abstract – This poster is about a project to share and receive guidance on Lebret Indian Residential School photos from the University of Saskatchewan to the Starblanket First Nation, Peepeekisis Cree Nation, Okanese First Nation, Little Black Bear First Nation, and Métis people in and around Lebret, Saskatchewan, Canada. A community engagement will be held at the same time as the Treaty 4 gathering in September 2025 to ask for appropriate descriptions to be able to repair metadata records and seek guidance for stewardship decisions around the photos. This poster will share the results of this first engagement along with reflections to improve future engagements. It will demonstrate the importance and necessity of incorporating Indigenous communities and Indigenous Knowledges into preservation practices and strategies to uphold Indigenous data sovereignty.

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I. POSTER ABSTRACT

In 2015, the Truth and Reconciliation Commission of Canada (TRC) released their final report which concluded that the establishment and operation of residential schools was a central element in Canada's cultural genocide against Indigenous Peoples [1]. The residential school system was funded by the government and operated by religious institutions to assimilate Indigenous children into Euro-Canadian culture. These children

were taken from their families and subject to abuse, disease, malnourishment, experimentation, and forced assimilation into colonial behaviors. The number of deaths is in the thousands and many of these children were buried in unmarked graves which are still in the process of being discovered [2]. The survivors gained life-long trauma from these experiences which turned into intergenerational trauma that rippled through their communities and led to The Indian Residential Schools Settlement Agreement, the largest class-action settlement in Canadian history, and the creation of the TRC [3]. This context is important for understanding the gravity of the situation and the significance of the University of Saskatchewan (USask) being in possession of residential school photos.

The University Archives and Special Collections (UASC) has four restricted photo albums dating between 1906 and 1963 that pertain to the students and staff at the Lebret Indian Residential School. The school affected the Starblanket First Nation, Peepeekisis Cree Nation, Okanese First Nation, Little Black Bear First Nation, and Métis people in and around Lebret, Saskatchewan, Canada. A community engagement will be held at the same time as Treaty 4 gatherings in September 2025 to make the communities aware about the existence of these photos, correct and enhance metadata records, and

seek guidance for stewardship decisions around the photos. We acknowledge these photos belong to the community and the future of these materials is ultimately their decision. We seek to support them however we can in the process of preserving these materials. As we work to create safer spaces for Indigenous Peoples within the USask Library and Archives, we understand that there are barriers to access that are unique to Indigenous Peoples. As per the Reconciliation Framework created by the Steering Committee on Canada's Archives, the onus is on us as institutions to reach out to Indigenous communities and establish the groundwork for a long-lasting relationship [4].

This project was initially prompted by Sadie Anderson, Indigenous Archivist, finding her grandfather in four different photos within these photo albums, all of which neither she nor her mother had seen before. This engagement will give the rest of her community a chance to have similar experiences, to see loved ones who are no longer with them or whom they never got the chance to meet. By sharing these photos with Indigenous communities whose children attended this school, we hope to give agency back to the survivors. Instead of being subject to colonialist narratives, these communities will have the power to tell their own stories and re-contextualize these photos [5].

This poster describes how we utilize Indigenous practices, Knowledges, and protocols to undertake reparative work *in a good way* with the Indigenous communities affected by this school to ensure that decisions around the preservation of these photos are guided by their needs for access and use. This methodology aligns with the principles of OAIS which asserts that the aim of preservation is to ensure that digital objects remain accessible and usable by the designated community [6]. In the case of this project, the designated community has particular cultural needs and a specific historical context that needs to be taken into account when it comes to access, use, and how the objects are understood. Advocating for Indigenous practices and consultation within digital preservation is important to ensure that Indigenous Peoples are not barred from accessing their own materials. Our poster will share the results of this first engagement along with reflections to improve

future engagements in the hopes that our experiences will benefit and encourage other digital preservation practitioners to embed Indigenous Knowledges and protocols within their own work.

REFERENCES

- [1] Truth and Reconciliation Commission. "The Final Report of the Truth and Reconciliation Commission of Canada," McGill Queen's Univ. Press, Montreal, Que, 2015.
- [2] Government of Canada. "Missing children and burial information." Canada.ca. <https://www.rcaanc-cirnac.gc.ca/eng/1524504992259/1557512149981> (accessed April 14, 2025).
- [3] Government of Canada. "Truth and Reconciliation Commission of Canada." Canada.ca. <https://www.rcaanc-cirnac.gc.ca/eng/1450124405592/1529106060525> (accessed April 14, 2025).
- [4] The Steering Committee on Canada's Archives. "Reconciliation Framework: Response to the Report of the Truth and Reconciliation Commission Taskforce." www.archives2026.com. https://archives2026.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/reconciliationframeworkreport_en.pdf (accessed April 14, 2025).
- [5] L. Tuhiwai-Smith. *Decolonizing Methodologies: Research and Indigenous Peoples*. London, UK: Zed Press Ltd, 1999.
- [6] The Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems, "Reference Model for an Open Archival Information System (OAIS)," CCSDS 650.0-M-3. Washington, DC, USA, December 2024.

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